

IMPROVING HEALTHCARE PROFESSIONALS' KNOWLEDGE AND SKILLS ON EARLY MANAGEMENT OF INVASIVE FUNGAL INFECTIONS IN NIGERIA: NEEDS ASSESSMENT AND STRATEGIC PLANNING

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ABSTRACT

Invasive fungal infection (IFI) is a life-threatening deep fungal infection that commonly affects immunocompromised or critically ill patients globally, especially in resource-limited settings such as Nigeria. This study aimed at evaluating context-specific gaps in the management of patients with IFIs, hence, a hospital-based cross-sectional survey was conducted in 8 hospitals across 8 States in Nigeria using a structured questionnaire. The results showed that 5(62.5%) hospitals have very few (< 3) or no specialists dedicated to their mycology benches. Three (37.5%) hospitals have no healthcare workers (HCWs) who have received training in mycosis, while 4(50%) hospitals have less than 6 HCWs who have received training in mycosis. Additionally, only 2(25%) hospitals have received less than 3 training support on mycosis diagnosis, whereas 6 (75%) of the hospitals never received any support at all. Six (75%), 4(50%), and 2(25%) of the hospitals respectively reported Candidiasis, Aspergillosis (the two common causes of IFIs), and Cutaneous mycosis as the most prevalent diagnosis cases in mycosis. This study, therefore, has identified areas (gaps) for improvement in the diagnosis and treatment of IFIs, which can be leveraged to raise knowledge of IFIs among HCWs and of course, enhance effective IFI treatment in hospital settings.

Keywords: Invasive Fungal Infections, Nigeria, Needs Assessment, Diagnostic Capacity, Knowledge Gaps, Resource-limited settings.

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INTRODUCTION

Invasive Fungal Infection (IFI) is a life-threatening deep fungal infection rather than a superficial, self-limiting, indolent, or localized fungal infection. Over 100,000 species of fungi exist, and about 300 of the species cause diseases in humans (Denham *et al.*, 2019). Globally, it is estimated that about 2 million people have Candida, Aspergillus, Cryptococcus, and Pneumocystis infections each year (Schmiedel *et al.*, 2016). These fungal organisms are the most prevalent, and are responsible for more than 90% of fatalities caused by fungus (Donnelly *et al.*, 2020). Over the years, fungal-related diseases are being neglected globally despite the high level of mortality and morbidity in at-risk communities (Rodrigues and Nosanchuk, 2020; Rayens and Norris, 2022).

According to Joe *et al.* (2011), a variety of fungal species that cause IFIs which are thought to be life-threatening illnesses, have become an increasingly common cause of opportunistic infections among immune-suppressed individuals all over the world. The last two decades have experienced a significant increase in the global incidence of IFIs, which has been attributed to the human immunodeficiency virus (HIV) pandemic, medical and oncological therapeutic advances, and the presence of better diagnostics for IFIs (Guarner, 2017).

In Africa, there is a lack of inexpensive diagnostic tests, and not many medical personnel or antifungal medications available, and vertical health systems on the continent contribute to deathblow from this disease as a result of poorly funded and overburdened health systems (GAFFI,

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12

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2022). In addition, the high burden of opportunistic fungal infections is a result of the high prevalence of HIV and tuberculosis in sub-Saharan Africa (Kuate *et al.*, 2021). According to statistics from 15 of the 57 African nations included in the Global Action Funds Fungal Infections study on invasive fungal infections (GAFFI, 2022), there are an estimated 47 million people living in Africa who have fungal diseases, of which 1.7 million are thought to have serious fungal infections every year.

In Nigeria, there are about 73,000 doctors registered with the Medical and Dental Council of Nigeria (MDCN) in 2020, with an estimated 200 million people to take care of (Oladele *et al.*, 2020). Despite having a high HIV and TB burden, Nigeria has a dearth of data on IFIs with gaps in their laboratory capacity for the diagnosis of IFIs, and it's estimated that each year, 11.8% of Nigerians contract these fungi with severe infection (Osaigbovo *et al.*, 2021, Oladele *et al.*, 2020)

Adda *et al.* (2022) conducted a needs assessment to establish baseline indicators on the performance of antimicrobial stewardship. Data and evidence from the study showed unmet needs and capacity gaps in 14 hospitals across Nigeria that responded to the survey. Furthermore, according to Oladele *et al.* (2014), the majority of the 1056 doctors sampled throughout Nigeria have a low degree of understanding about IFIs diagnosis. Doctors with more years of experience were more knowledgeable about IFI management. The study further showed that there are significant knowledge gaps about IFIs among Nigerian doctors, which are likely to have a negative effect on patients with serious clinical problems.

IFIs are largely neglected globally with limited data in spite of the burden. The lack of data and the dearth of national surveillance programs make it difficult to combat these diseases. There is an urgent need for economically viable diagnostic models and solutions, as well as capacity building. Hence, this study designed to evaluate context-specific gaps in the diagnosis and treatment of IFIs across 8 hospitals in Nigeria namely; Abubakar Tafawa Balewa University Teaching Hospital (ATBUTH) Bauchi, Benue State University Teaching Hospital (BSUTH) Makurdi, Federal Teaching Hospital (FTH) Gombe, DalhatuAraf Specialist Hospital (DASH) Lafia, Jos University Teaching Hospital (JUTH) Jos, University of Abuja Teaching Hospital (UATH), Usman Danfodiyo University Teaching Hospital (UDUTH) Sokoto, and Federal Medical Centre (FMC) Jalingo. The findings can support the

development of educational programs that will address context-specific gaps in the early diagnosis and treatment of patients with IFIs.

METHODOLOGY

Study Design: A facility-based cross-sectional survey was conducted evaluating the hospitals' capacity and context-specific gaps in the diagnosis and treatment of patients with invasive molds and yeast infection (mycology). The needs assessment was conducted in 8 tertiary hospitals from 8 States and FCT (Abuja, Bauchi, Benue, Gombe, Plateau, Sokoto, Nasarawa, and Taraba) across 3 geopolitical zones in Nigeria, using a structured questionnaire.

Mode of data Collection: The questionnaire was administered to the hospitals between the periods of September 2022 to January 2023 by certified Centre for Initiative and Development (CFID) assessors through the top management (CMD, CMAC, DCMAC) of each hospital to respond to the tool. The study targeted the hospital's mycology bench, the specialists dedicated to the bench, and the existing diagnostic capacity of mycosis in the said hospital's laboratory.

Ethical Consideration: Ethical approval was obtained from the National Health Research Ethics Committee (NHREC), with NHREC Protocol Number: NHREC/01/01/2007-09/10/2023 and NHREC Approval Number: NHREC/01/01/2007-08/11/20233. Informed consent was obtained from each participant before the observation of any consultations. Consent was also obtained from the Nigeria Centre for Disease Control (NCDC).

Statistical Analysis: The responses from the hospitals of interest were evaluated, and only completed and reverted tools were factored into this study. The data were coded and analyzed using a Microsoft Excel Package and summarized with the use of descriptive statistics such as simple percentages, cross-tabulations, and frequency distribution.

RESULTS

The needs assessment was conducted in 8 facilities; all of which are tertiary hospitals in Nigeria. According to Table 1, all the 8 hospitals (100%) are capable of diagnosing invasive molds and yeast infections. Seven (87.5%) of the

TABLE 1: FREQUENCY DISTRIBUTION OF RESPONSES FROM EIGHT HOSPITALS ACROSS EIGHT STATES IN NIGERIA

Key Questions	Categories	Frequency/Percentage (%)
Current capacity in the diagnosis of invasive molds and yeasts infection (YES/NO)	YES	8(100%)
	NO	0(0%)
Existing dedicated mycology bench in the medical laboratory (YES/NO)	YES	7(87.5%)
	NO	1(12.5%)
Current capacity/ number of specialists dedicated to the mycology bench	0	1(12.5%)
	<3	4(50%)
	3 – 6	3(37.5%)
Number of HCWs that have received training on diagnosis and treatment of IFIs	0	3(37.5%)
	< 2	0(0%)
	2 – 5	4(50%)
	> 6	1(12.5%)
Number of training support your hospital had received on the diagnosis of mycoses	0	6(75%)
	1	1(12.5%)
	2	1(12.5%)
Most prevalence diagnosis cases in mycoses	Candida	7(87.5%)
	Aspergillus	4(50%)
	Cutaneous mycosis	2(25%)
	Opportunistic mycosis	1(12.5%)

Hospitals have existing dedicated mycology benches in their respective medical laboratory, while only 1(12.5%) does not.

Table 1 also shows the number of specialists dedicated to the mycology bench in the studied hospitals. Four of the hospitals (n=4; 50%) have less than 3 specialists dedicated to their mycology benches. Three hospitals (n=3; 37.5%) have between 3 to 6 specialists dedicated to their mycology benches, whereas 1(12.5%) has no specialist dedicated to its mycology bench. Also, in Table 1, is the number of healthcare workers (HCWs) across the studied hospitals that have ever received training on mycosis. Three of the hospitals (n=3; 37.5%) have no HCWs that have ever received training in mycosis. Four of the hospitals (n=4; 50%) have between 2 – 5 HCWs that have received training in mycosis, while only 1(12.5%) of the hospitals with 11 HCWs had received training in mycosis.

Furthermore, Table 1 shows that 6 (75%) of the hospitals have never received training support on the diagnosis of mycosis. In two separate instances, only 1 hospital (12.5%) received training support once, and twice, respectively.

On the prevalence of IFIs disease entities across the hospitals (as seen in Table 1), 6(75%) of the hospitals reported that Candidiasis was one of the most diagnosed cases in mycosis. Aspergillosis was reported by 4(50%) of the hospitals, while Cutaneous mycosis was reported by 2(25%) of the hospitals.

DISCUSSIONS

Findings from this study confirm the existence of gaps in diagnostic capacity and knowledge gaps in early diagnosis and management of IFIs, largely due to a lack of capacity-building (training gaps) and a lack of non-culture-based diagnostic capacity in the hospitals across Nigeria. These findings may have a direct link to the paucity of data (WHO FPPL, 2022) and paucity of national surveillance programs that impedes the fight against IFIs in Nigeria, and by extension, sub-Saharan Africa. Interestingly, a five-year retrospective study by Wen *et al.* (2022), on IFIs at a tertiary hospital in China, had shown limited data on clinical diagnosis and treatment of deep fungal infections.

As regards mycological infection diagnosis, the observed lack of diagnostic capacity and training gaps does indicate that superficial mycosis was the recurrent diagnosis, while

invasive fungal infections were largely negligible. This is similar to the result obtained from a ten-year retrospective study by Oladele *et al.* (2013) on mycological infections at a major tertiary hospital in Nigeria, wherein there was no diagnosis of IFI disease throughout the period of the study.

From an earlier ten-year retrospective study at a major tertiary hospital in Nigeria on mycological infections, Oladele *et al.* (2013) reported that superficial mycosis was the recurrent diagnosis, while invasive fungal infections were largely neglected. In fact, throughout the period of the study, there was no diagnosis of an IFI disease made. This relates to a lack of diagnostic capacity and training gaps as revealed in this study.

The current study also shows that very few numbers of HCWs had ever received training on the diagnosis and treatment of IFIs. Strikingly, in 3 of the hospitals, constituting 37.5%, none of the healthcare workers (HCWs) were ever trained. In contrast, only 1 hospital, representing 12.5%, has the highest number of trained HCWs at 11, while the remaining 4 hospitals, which make up 50%, have 5 or fewer HCWs who have ever received training. Furthermore, in this study of 8 tertiary facilities, 6 (representing 75%) have never received training support for the diagnosis of mycoses. These can be attributed to the fact that healthcare facilities are not receiving adequate training support on IFI, hence, the knowledge gaps reported by Oladele *et al.* (2020) on IFIs among Nigerian clinicians.

Among the eight hospitals in this study that have a current capacity in the diagnosis of invasive molds and yeast infection, only 2(25%) reported the availability of diagnostic techniques in their medical laboratory; most of which are the conventional approach, while the other 6(75%) hospitals have no data on such diagnostic techniques. This starkly illustrates the paucity of invasive fungal infection (IFI) diagnostic practices. Conventional techniques such as the culture-based diagnostic tests, histopathology, and microscopy, rely majorly on a healthcare professional's skill and high level of expertise in the detection/identification of fungal and fungal-related disease. This is not practically possible across all settings, especially in limited resource settings like sub-Saharan Africa, hence, the importance and necessity of non-culture approaches such as antigen detection, fungal antibody, and nucleic acid detection (Fang *et al.*, 2023).

This study also assessed the number of specialists dedicated to the mycology bench across the 8 hospitals in Nigeria. The data revealed a very scanty number dedicated to their benches, 4(62.5%) of the hospitals have less than three (3) specialist dedicated to their benches. In fact, one of the hospitals 1(12.5%) has no specialists dedicated to their bench. This finding agrees with the GAFFI (2022) in-depth situational survey to evaluate comprehensively the availability of fungal disease diagnostics and treatment in Africa. The result shows that fungal disease is being neglected continually despite the high mortality and morbidity in at-risk populations.

Several studies WHO, FPPL (2022); Firacative (2020); William *et al.*, (2013); Fang *et al.*, (2023); Hagan.,(2018); Michael *et al.*, (2006) reported that the common pathogens that cause IFIs are *Candida*, *Aspergillus*, and *Cryptococcus*, ranking *Candida* as the most. It is interesting to note that the result of the current study reflects the prevalence cases of these pathogens across all the hospitals. As invasive as they are, they are the most prevalent cases in the hospitals of interest in this study. Out of the 8(100%) hospitals, *Candida* is prevalent in 7(87.5%) followed by *Aspergillus* 4(50%). It was observed that diagnostic tests are expensive, sluggish, often missed out, and frequently have limited sensitivity and/or specificity. Consequently, it is essential to raise knowledge of IFIs among healthcare workers so that they are taken into account when making differential diagnoses, especially among at-risk populations. Furthermore, the introduction of non-culture-based diagnostics techniques cannot be over emphasized. This will enhance the overall diagnostic precision that is necessary for the effective management of IFIs.

CONCLUSION

Invasive fungal infections receive extremely little attention and resources despite emerging concerns, and the lack of high-quality data. Considering the fact that fungal pathogens are spreading more widely, fungus-related infections pose a serious threat to public health. The result from this study reflects serious gaps in IFIs diagnostic capacity in the studied facilities and training/knowledge gaps in the said hospitals across Nigeria. These findings relate to the 2022 WHO Fungal Priority Pathogens Listreport, which shows that rapid and accurate diagnostics are rare for fungal diseases, and those that do exist, are either expensive or not generally accessible globally, especially in resource-limited settings. This

underscores the urgent need for further research, development, and public health actions. This study, therefore, has found areas (gaps) for improvement in the diagnosis and treatment of IFIs, which can be leveraged to enhance effective IFI management in hospital settings.

RECOMMENDATIONS:

- Increased availability and accessibility of advanced non-culture-based diagnostic techniques, such as antigen detection, fungal antibody, and nucleic acid detection, in tertiary hospitals and other health care facilities.
- Provision of comprehensive educational training for health care professionals on the epidemiology, diagnosis, treatment, and prevention of invasive fungal infections, especially among high-risk populations such as HIV and tuberculosis patients.
- Establish a national surveillance program and a data repository for invasive fungal infections, to monitor the incidence, prevalence, mortality, morbidity, and antifungal resistance patterns of these infections in Nigeria.

AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS:

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